

Citation	Contributor	Defined family	Level	Appreciated overall quality	Impact assessment method	LCIA info					Study type	LCA	LCC	I-O
						CML family	ReCiPe family	ILCD family	Other LCIA					
Adom, Felix K., and Jennifer B. Dunn. "Life Cycle Analysis of Corn-Stover-Derived Polymer-Grade L-Lactic Acid and Ethyl Lactate: Greenhouse Gas Emissions and Fossil Energy Consumption", <i>Biofuels, Bioproducts and Biorefining</i> , Vol. 11, 2017, pp. 258–268	AUA	Platforms obtained by fermentation route	Platform	-	??						1	LCA	1	
Cok, Benjamin, Ioannis Tsiropoulos, Alexander L. Roes, and Martin K. Patel. "Succinic Acid Production Derived from Carbohydrates: An Energy and Greenhouse Gas Assessment of a Platform Chemical toward a Bio-Based Economy", <i>Biofuels, Bioproducts and Biorefining</i> , Vol. 8, No. 1, 2014, pp. 16–29	AUA	Platforms obtained by fermentation route	Platform	-							1	LCA	1	
Dros, A. B., O. Larue, A. Reimond, F. De Campo, and M. Pera-Titus. "Hexamethylenediamine (HMDA) from Fossil- vs. Bio-Based Routes: An Economic and Life Cycle Assessment Comparative Study", <i>Green Chemistry</i> , Vol. 17, No. 10, October 2, 2015, pp. 4760–4772	UoY	Platforms obtained by other routes	Platform	-	Custom set						1	LCA	1	
Ekman, Anna, and Pal Börjesson. "Environmental Assessment of Propionic Acid Produced in an Agricultural Biomass-Based Biorefinery System", <i>Journal of Cleaner Production</i> , Vol. 19, No. 11, 2011, pp. 1257–1265	AUA	Platforms obtained by fermentation route	Platform	-	??						1	LCA	1	
Forté, Annachiara, Amalia Zucaro, Riccardo Basosi, and Angelo Fierro. "LCA of 1,4-Butanediol Produced via Direct Fermentation of Sugars from Wheat Straw Feedstock within a Territorial Biorefinery", <i>Materials</i> , Vol. 9, No. 7, 2016, pp. 1–22.	AUA	Platforms obtained by fermentation route	Platform	-	ReCiPe (v.1.10, 2013) midpoint hierarchic		1				0	LCA	1	
Gezae Dafu, Asfaw, and Johann F. G?rgens. "Techno-Economic Analysis and Environmental Impact Assessment of Lignocellulosic Lactic Acid Production", <i>Chemical Engineering Science</i> , Vol. 162, 2017, pp. 53–65. http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.ces.2016.12.054	AUA	Platforms obtained by fermentation route	Platform	-	ReCiPe Midpoint(H)			1			0	LCA	1	
Groot, Wim J., and Tobias Boren. "Life Cycle Assessment of the Manufacture of Lactide and PLA Biopolymers from Sugarcane in Thailand", <i>International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment</i> , Vol. 15, No. 9, 2010, pp. 970–984.	AUA	Platforms obtained by fermentation route	Platform	-	Custom set						1	LCA	1	
Kho, Hsien Hui, Reginald B H Tan, and Kevin W L Chng. "Environmental Impacts of Conventional Plastic and Bio-Based Carrier Bags", <i>International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment</i> , Vol. 15, No. 3, 2010, pp. 284–293.	AUA	Platforms obtained by fermentation route	Platform	-	Environmental Development of Industrial Products 2003 impact						1	LCA	1	
Koller, Martin, Daniel Sandholzer, Anna Salerno, Gerhart Braunege, and Michael Narodslawsky. "Biopolymer from Industrial Residues: Life Cycle Assessment of Poly(hydroxyalkanoates) from Whey", <i>Resources, Conservation and Recycling</i> , Vol. 73, 2013, pp. 64–71. http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2013.01.017	AUA	Platforms obtained by fermentation route	Platform	-	Narodslawsky and Krottschek (1995)						1	LCA	1	
Lokesh, K., C. West, I. Kuylenstierna, J. Fan, V. Butarin, P. Priezel, J. A. Lopez-Sanchez, and J. Clark. "Environmental Impact Assessment of Wheat Straw Based Alkyl Polyglycolates Produced Using Novel Chemical Approaches", <i>Green Chemistry</i> , Vol. 19, No. 18, September 19, 2017, pp. 4380–4395	UoY	Platforms obtained by other routes	Platform	-	metrics from Green chemistry (?)						1	LCA	1	
Madival, Santosh, Rafael Auras, Sher Paul Singh, and Ramani Narayan. "Assessment of the Environmental Profile of PLA, PET and PS Clamshell Containers Using LCA Methodology", <i>Journal of Cleaner Production</i> , Vol. 17, No. 13, 2009, pp. 1183–1194. http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2009.03.015	AUA	Platforms obtained by fermentation route	Platform	-	??						1	LCA	1	
Morales, Merten, Pierre Y Dapsens, Isabella Giovinozzo, Julia Witte, Cecilia Mondelli, Stavros Papaioakantakis, Konrad Hungerbühler, and Javier Perez-Ramirez. "Environmental and Economic Assessment of Lactic Acid Production from Glycerol Using Cascade Bio- and Chemoanalysis", <i>Energy & Environmental Science</i> , Vol. 8, No. 2, 2015, pp. 558–567. http://dx.doi.org/10.1039/C4EE03352E	AUA	Platforms obtained by fermentation route	Platform	-	Eco-indicator 99						1	LCA	1	
Morgan-Sagastume, Fernando, Sara Heimerson, Giuseppe Laera, Alan Werker, and Magdalena Swanström. "Techno-Environmental Assessment of Integrating Polyhydroxyalkanoate (PHA) Production with Services of Municipal Wastewater Treatment", <i>Journal of Cleaner Production</i> , Vol. 137, 2016, pp. 1368–1381	AUA	Platforms obtained by fermentation route	Platform	-	??						1	LCA	1	
Moussa, Hassan I., Ali Elkamel, and Steven B. Young. "Assessing Energy Performance of Bio-Based Succinic Acid Production Using LCA", <i>Journal of Cleaner Production</i> , Vol. 139, 2016, pp. 761–769	AUA	Platforms obtained by fermentation route	Platform	-	??						1	LCA	1	
Mu, Dongyan, Thomas Seager, P. Suresh Rao, and Fu Zhao. "Comparative Life Cycle Assessment of Lignocellulosic Ethanol Production: Biochemical versus Thermochemical Conversion", <i>Environmental Management</i> , Vol. 46, No. 4, 2010, pp. 565–578.	AUA	Platforms obtained by fermentation route	Platform	-	not defined						1	LCA	1	
Parajuli, Ranjan, Marie-Treffman Knudsen, Martin Brink, Sylvie Njakou Djomo, Andrea Corona, and Tommy Dalgaard. "Environmental Impacts of Producing Bioethanol and Biobased Lactic Acid from Standaalone and Integrated Biorefineries Using a Consequential and an Attributional Life Cycle Assessment Approach", <i>Science of the Total Environment</i> , Vol. 598, 2017, pp. 497–512.	AUA	Platforms obtained by fermentation route	Platform	-	"EPD" method (Environdec, 2013) and ReCiPe			1			0	LCA	1	
Ponder, Celia, and Michael Overcash. "Cradle-to-Gate Life Cycle Inventory of Vancomycin Hydrochloride", <i>Science of the Total Environment</i> , Vol. 408, No. 6, 2010, pp. 1331–1337	AUA	Platforms obtained by fermentation route	Platform	-	??						1	LCA	1	
Sheldon, Roger A. "Utilisation of Biomass for Sustainable Fuels and Chemicals: Molecules, Methods and Metrics", <i>Catalysis Today</i> , Vol. 167, No. 1, Utilisation of Biomass for Fuels and Chemicals: The Road to Sustainability, June 10, 2011, pp. 3–13.	UoY	Platforms obtained by other routes	Platform	-	New methodology						1	Special and LCA	1	
Singh, Anoop, Deepak Pant, Nicholas E. Korres, Abdul-Sattar Nizami, Shiv Prasad, and Jerry D. Murphy. "Key Issues in Life Cycle Assessment of Ethanol Production from Lignocellulosic Biomass: Sun, Xiao-Zheng, Tomoko Minowa, Katsunobu Yamaguchi, and Yutaka Genchi. "Evaluation of Energy Consumption and Greenhouse Gas Emissions from Poly(phenylactic Acid) Production Using Sweet Sorghum", <i>Journal of Cleaner Production</i> , Vol. 87, 2015, pp. 208–215.	AUA	Platforms obtained by fermentation route	Platform	-	similar to others (1)						1	LCA	1	
Tufvesson Par, Anna Ekman, Roya R.R Sardari, Kristina Engdahl, and Linda Tufvesson. "Economic and Environmental Assessment of Propionic Acid Production by Fermentation Using Different Renewable Raw Materials", <i>Bioresour. Technology</i> , Vol. 149, 2013, pp. 556–564	AUA	Platforms obtained by fermentation route	Platform	-	??						1	LCA	1	
Adom, Felix, Jennifer B. Dunn, Jeongwoo Han, and Norm Sather. "Life-Cycle Fossil Energy Consumption and Greenhouse Gas Emissions of Bioderived Chemicals and Their Conventional Counterparts", <i>Environmental Science & Technology</i> , Vol. 48, No. 24, December 16, 2014, pp. 14624–14631	UoY	Fine and bulk chemicals	Product	-	Custom set						1	LCA	1	
Akiyama, Minoru, Takeharu Tsuge, and Yoshiharu Doi. "Environmental life cycle comparison of polyhydroxyalkanoates produced from renewable carbon resources by bacterial fermentation", <i>Polymer Degradation and Stability</i> , Vol. 80, No. 1, 2003, pp. 183–194.	UniBo	Plastic polymers (non-fibre)	Product	-	Custom set						1	LCA	1	
Batouli, Seyed Mostafa, Yimin Zhu, Mangesh Nar, and Nandika Anne D'Souza. "Environmental Performance of Kenaf-Fiber Reinforced Polyurethane: A Life Cycle Assessment Approach", <i>Journal Of Cleaner Production</i> , Vol. 66, 2014, pp. 164–173.	USC	Others	Product	-	Building for Environmental and Economic Sustainability (BEES)						1	LCA	1	
Belboom, Sandra, and Angélique Léonard. "Does biobased polymer achieve better environmental impacts than fossil polymer? Comparison of fossil HDPE and biobased HDPE produced from sugar beet and wheat", <i>Biomass and Bioenergy</i> , Vol. 85, 2016, pp. 159–167.	UniBo	Plastic polymers (non-fibre)	Product	-	Custom set						1	LCA	1	
Chen, Luyi, Rylie E.o. Pelton, and Timothy M. Smith. "Comparative life cycle assessment of fossil and bio-based polyethylene terephthalate (PET) bottles", <i>Journal of Cleaner Production</i> , Vol. 137, 2015, pp. 667–676.	UniBo	Plastic polymers (non-fibre)	Product	-	TRACI v2.1, ReCiPe v1.08, ILCD 2011			1	1		0	LCA	1	
Feijoo, S., S. González-García, J.M. Lema, and M.T. Moreira. "Life Cycle Assessment Of B-Galactosidase Enzyme Production", <i>Journal Of Cleaner Production</i> , Vol. 165, 2017, pp. 204–212.	USC	Proteins	Product	-	Recipe midpoint			1			0	LCA	1	
Fernández-Dacosta, Cora, John A. Posada, Robbert Kleerebezem, Maria C. Cuellar, and Andrea Ramirez. "Microbial community-based polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) production from wastewater: Techno-Economic analysis and ex-ante environmental assessment", <i>Bioresour. Technology</i> , Vol. 185, 2015, pp. 368–377.	UniBo	Plastic polymers (non-fibre)	Product	-	Custom set						1	LCC and LCA	1	1

Fiorentino, G., M. Ripa, S. Mellino, S. Fahd, and S. Ulgati, "Life Cycle Assessment of Brassica Carinata Biomass Conversion to Bioenergy and Platform Chemicals", <i>Journal of Cleaner Production</i> , Vol. 66, No. Supplement C, March 1, 2014, pp. 174-187.	UoY	Fine and bulk chemicals	Product	-	CML 2001 and Cumulative Energy demand	1				0	LCA		1		
Gilpin, Geoffrey S., and Anders S. G. Andrae, "Comparative Attributional Life Cycle Assessment Of European Cellulase Enzyme Production For Use In Second-Generation Lignocellulosic Bioethanol Production", <i>The International Journal Of Life Cycle Assessment</i> , Vol. 22, No. 7, 2016, pp. 1034-1053	USC	Proteins	Product	-	CML 1A baseline and non-baseline methods along with cumulative	1				0	LCA		1		
González-García, Sara, Gumersindo Feijoo, Carol Heathcote, Andreas Kandelbauer, and M. Teresa Moreira, "Environmental Assessment Of Green Hardboard Production Coupled With A Lacase Activated System", <i>Journal Of Cleaner Production</i> , Vol. 19, No. 5, 2011, p	USC	Others	Product	-	CML 2 baseline 2000 V2.1 biogenic method	1				0	LCA		1		
H. Khoo, H. W. L. Ee, and Valerio Isoni, "Bio-Chemicals from Lignocellulose Feedstock: Sustainability, LCA and the Green Conundrum", <i>Green Chemistry</i> , Vol. 18, No. 7, 2016, pp. 1912-1922	UoY	Fine and bulk chemicals	Product	-	Custom set					1	LCA		1		
Harding, K, J Dennis, H Vonblottnitz, and S Harrison, "Environmental analysis of plastic production processes: Comparing petroleum-based polypropylene and polyethylene with biologically-based poly-β-Hydroxybutyric acid using life cycle analysis," <i>Journal of Biotechnology</i> Vol. 130, No. 1, 2007, pp. 57-66.	UniBo	Plastic polymers (non-fibre)	Product	-	CML 2 Baseline 2000 V2.03	1				0	LCA		1		
Jeswani, Harish K., Termitope Falano, and Adisa Azapagic, "Life Cycle Environmental Sustainability of Lignocellulosic Ethanol Produced in Integrated Thermo-Chemical Biorefineries", <i>Biofuels, Bioproducts and Biorefining</i> , Vol. 9, No. 6, November 1, 2015, pp. 661-67	UoY	Fine and bulk chemicals	Product	-	Custom set					1	LCA		1		
Kim, Seungdo, Concepción Jiménez-González, and Bruce E. Dale, "Enzymes For Pharmaceutical Applications—A Cradle-To-Gate Life Cycle Assessment", <i>The International Journal Of Life Cycle Assessment</i> , Vol. 14, No. 5, 2009, pp. 392-400.	USC	Proteins	Product	-	CML (Guinée 2002)	1				0	LCA		1		
Kit, Yoong, Leong Pau, and Loke Show, "Economic and Environmental Analysis of PHAs Production Process", <i>Clean Technologies and Environmental Policy</i> , Vol. 19, No. 7, 2017, pp. 1941-1953.	AUA	Plastic polymers (non-fibre)	Product	-	??					1	LCA		1		
La Rosa, A.D., G. Cozzo, A. Latteri, A. Recca, A. Björklund, E. Parrinello, and G. Cicala, "Life Cycle Assessment Of A Novel Hybrid Glass-Hemp/Thermoset Composite", <i>Journal Of Cleaner Production</i> , Vol. 44, 2013, pp. 69-76.	USC	Others	Product	-	ReCiPe	1				0	SLCA and LCA		1		
Leceta, I, A. Etxabide, S. Cabezudo, K. De La Caba, and P. Guerrero, "Bio-based films prepared with by-products and wastes: environmental assessment", <i>Journal of Cleaner Production</i> Vol. 64, 2014, pp. 218-227.	UniBo	Plastic polymers (non-fibre)	Product	-	Eco-Indicator 99 (Hierarchist)					1	LCA		1		
Madival, Santosh, Rafael Auras, Sher Paul Singh, and Ramani Narayan, "Assessment of the environmental profile of PLA, PET and PS clamshell containers using LCA methodology", <i>Journal of Cleaner Production</i> , Vol. 17, No. 13, 2009, pp. 1183-1194.	UniBo	Plastic polymers (non-fibre)	Product	-	IMPACT 2002+					1	LCA		1		
Marinussen and Kool, "Environmental impacts of synthetic amino acid production", report from Blonk Milieuv Advies BV, 2010 Netherlands	USC	Proteins	Product	-	ReCiPe 2008	1				0	LCA		1		
Ministry of environment and food of Denmark, Danish Environmental Protection Agency "Novo Nordisk's Environmental Profit and Loss account", 2014 http://mtd.dkt.service/publikationer/publikationsarkiv/2014/apr/assessment-of-potentials-and-limitations-in-valuation-of-externalities	USC	Proteins	Product	-	Custom set					1	LCC and LCA and IO		1	1	1
Nielsen, Per H., Karen M. Ouenball, and Henrik Wenzel, "Cradle-To-Gate Environmental Assessment Of Enzyme Products Produced Industrially In Denmark By Novozymes A/S", <i>The International Journal Of Life Cycle Assessment</i> , Vol. 12, No. 6, 2006, pp. 432-438.	USC	Proteins	Product	-	Eco-indicator 95 v2.1.					1	LCA		1		
Oxenboll, K.M., K. Pontoppida, and F. Fru-Nji, "Use Of A Protease In Poultry Feed Offers Promising Environmental Benefits", <i>International Journal Of Poultry Science</i> , Vol. 10, No. 11, 2011, pp. 842-848.	USC	Proteins	Product	-	CML baseline 2000	1				0	LCA		1		
Papong, Seksan, Pomthong Malakul, Ruethai Trungkavshirakun, Pechda Wenunun, Tassaneewan Chom-In, Manit Nithitanakul, and Ed Sarobol, "Comparative assessment of the environmental profile of PLA and PET drinking water bottles from a life cycle perspective", <i>Journal of Cleaner Production</i> , Vol. 65, 2014, pp. 539-550.	UniBo	Plastic polymers (non-fibre)	Product	-	CML 2 baseline 2000	1				0	LCA		1		
Pargana, Nuno, Manuel Duarte Pinheiro, José Dinis Silvestre, and Jorge de Brito, "Comparative Environmental Life Cycle Assessment of Thermal Insulation Materials Of Buildings", <i>Energy And Buildings</i> , Vol. 82, 2014, pp. 466-481.	USC	Others	Product	-	CML 2001	1				0	LCA		1		
Pérez-López, P., S. González-García, C. Jeffryes, S.N. Agathos, E. McHugh, D. Walsh, P. Murray, S. Moano, G. Feijoo, and M.T. Moreira, "Life Cycle Assessment Of The Production Of The Red Antioxidant Carotenoid Astaxanthin By Microalgae: From Lab To Pilot Scale", <i>Journal Of Cleaner Production</i> , Vol. 64, 2014, pp. 332-344.	USC	Proteins	Product	-	CML 2001	1				0	LCA		1		
Pérez-López, Paula, Sara González-García, R. Gabriela Ulloa, Jorge Sineiro, Gumersindo Feijoo, and M.T. Teresa Moreira, "Life Cycle Assessment Of The Production Of Bioactive Compounds From Tetraselmis Suecica At Pilot Scale", <i>Journal Of Cleaner Production</i> , Vol. 64, 2014, pp. 323-331.	USC	Proteins	Product	-	CML 2 baseline 2000 V2.04	1				0	LCA		1		
Pursula, Tina, and Minna Päällysaho, Report: LCA Of Enzyme Production And Calculation Of Key Performance Indicators For Metgen, Gaia Consulting Oy, 2016. http://www.metgen.com/wp-content/uploads/2017/01/Final-report-LCA-and-KPIs-for-enzyme-production-18.11.2016.pdf	USC	Proteins	Product	-	CML 1A* methodology	1				0	LCA		1		
Qiang, Tao, Demei Yu, Anjiang Zhang, Honghong Gao, Zhao Li, Zengchao Liu, Weixing Chen, and Zhen Han, "Life Cycle Assessment On Polylactide-Based Wood Plastic Composites Toughened With Polyhydroxyalkanoate", <i>Journal Of Cleaner Production</i> , Vol. 66, 2014, pp. 139-145	USC	Others	Product	-	Attribute hierarchy model (AHM)					1	LCA		1		
Razza, Francesco, Francesco Degli Innocenti, Antonio Dobon, Cesar Allaga, Carmen Sanchez, and Mercedes Hortal, "Environmental profile of a bio-based and biodegradable foamed packaging prototype in comparison with the current benchmark", <i>Journal of Cleaner Production</i> , Vol. 102, 2015, pp. 493-500.	UniBo	Plastic polymers (non-fibre)	Product	-	Custom set					1	LCA		1		
Sierra-Pérez, Jorge, Jesús Boschmonat-Ribes, Ana C. Dias, and Xavier Gabarrell, "Environmental implications Of The Use Of Agglomerated Cork As Thermal Insulation In Buildings", <i>Journal Of Cleaner Production</i> , Vol. 126, 2016, pp. 97-107.	USC	Others	Product	-	Hierarchical approach of CML 2002	1				0	LCA		1		
Slater, C. Stewart, Mariano J. Savelski, David Hitchcock, and Eduardo J. Cavanagh, "Environmental Analysis of the Life Cycle Emissions of 2-Methyl Tetrahydrofuran Solvent Manufactured from Renewable Resources", <i>Journal of Environmental Science and Health, Part A</i> , Vol. 51, No. 6, May 11, 2016, pp. 487-494.	UoY	Fine and bulk chemicals	Product	-	Custom set					1	LCA		1		
Tsiropoulos, I., A.p.c. Faaï, L. Lundquist, U. Schenker, J.F. Briois, and M.k. Patel, "Life cycle impact assessment of bio-based plastics from sugarcane ethanol", <i>Journal of Cleaner Production</i> , Vol. 90, 2015, pp. 114-127.	UniBo	Plastic polymers (non-fibre)	Product	-	Impact 2002+; Pfister et al. (2009) for water use (endpoint).					1	LCA		1		
Vink, Erwin T H, Steve Davies, and Jeffrey J. Kolstad, "The Eco-Profile for Current Ingeo Polylactide Production", <i>Industrial Biotechnology</i> , Vol. 6, No. 4, 2010, pp. 212-224	AUA	Plastic polymers (non-fibre)	Product	-	??					1	LCA		1		
Wilson, James B., Eric T. Sakimoto, "Gate-to-gate life-cycle inventory of softwood plywood production" <i>Wood and Fiber Science, Society of Wood Science and Technology</i> , 37 Corrim Special Issue, 2005, pp. 58-73	USC	Others	Product	-	Inventory only					1	LCA		1		
Zhang, Yanan, Guojing Hu, and Robert C. Brown, "Life Cycle Assessment of Commodity Chemical Production from Forest Residue via Fast Pyrolysis", <i>The International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment</i> , Vol. 19, No. 7, July 1, 2014, pp. 1371-1381	UoY	Fine and bulk chemicals	Product	-	TRACI 2.0					1	LCA		1		
Agyekum, Eric Ofori, K.p.j. (Karen) Fortuin, and Eugenie Van Der Harst, "Environmental and social life cycle assessment of bamboo bicycle frames made in Ghana," <i>Journal of Cleaner Production</i> Vol. 143, 2017, pp. 1069-1080	ECOS	Fibres	Raw material	-	UNEP/SETAC, 2009 and 2013, CML Baseline 2001	1				0	SLCA and LCA		1		

Arrigoni, Alessandro, Renato Pelosato, Paco Meli, Gianluca Ruggieri, Sergio Sabbadini, and Giovanni Dotelli, "Life cycle assessment of natural building materials: the role of carbonation, mixture components and transport in the environmental impacts of hempcrete blocks," <i>Journal of Benedikt Buchpries, Martin Kaltschmitt, "Life cycle assessment of bioethanol from wheat and sugar beet discussing environmental impacts of multiple concepts of co-product processing in the context of the European Renewable Energy Directive", Biofuels, Vol 7, No 2, 2016, pp. 141-153, DOI:</i>	ECOS	Fibres	Raw material	-	CML-IA Baseline	1					0	LCA	1	
Beneditkt Buchpries, Martin Kaltschmitt, "Life cycle assessment of bioethanol from wheat and sugar beet discussing environmental impacts of multiple concepts of co-product processing in the context of the European Renewable Energy Directive", <i>Biofuels, Vol 7, No 2, 2016, pp. 141-153, DOI:</i>	UWM	Sugars and starch (non-polymerized)	Raw material	good	ReCiPe	1					0	LCA	1	
Carmen Galan-Marin, Carlos Rivera-Gomez and Antonio Garcia-Martinez, (2016) "Use of Natural-Fiber Bio-Composites in Construction versus Traditional Solutions: Operational and Embodied Energy Assessment," <i>Materials</i> 9, 465-10	ECOS	Fibres	Raw material	-	CML 2001	1					0	LCA	1	
Chan et al., 2015 (palm oil, bio-oil with undefined use, LCA)	UniBo	Oils (non-polymerized)	Raw material	-	Custom set						1	LCA	1	
Cherubini, Francesco and Ugliati, Sergio, "Crop residues as raw materials for biorefinery systems - A LCA case study", <i>Applied Energy, Vol. 87, 2017, pp. 47-57.</i>	UniBo	Oils (non-polymerized)	Raw material	-	CML 2 baseline 2000 V2.03	1					0	LCA	1	
Cosate de Andrade, Marina F., Souza, Patricia M.F., Cavelett, Otavio, and Morales, Ana R. "Life Cycle Assessment of Poly(Lactic Acid) (PLA): Comparison Between Chemical Recycling, Mechanical Recycling and Composting", <i>Journal of Polymers and the Environment, Vol. 24, No. 4, 2016, pp. 372-384</i>	UWM	Sugars and starch (non-polymerized)	Raw material	-	Recipe, Cumulative Energy Demand (CED)	1					0	LCA	1	
Diego Magalhães do Nascimento, Amanda Ferreira Dias, Celso Pires de Araújo Junior, Morsyleide de Freitas Rosa, João Paulo Saraiva Morais, Maria Cláudia Brito de Figueirêdo: "A comprehensive approach for obtaining cellulose nanocrystal from cocoon fiber. Part II: Environmental assessment of technological pathways", <i>Industrial Crops and Products Volume 93, 25 December 2016, pp. 58-65</i>	ECOS	Fibres	Raw material	-	ReCiPe Midpoint (H)	1					0	LCA	1	
Gilani, Banafsheh, Stuart, Paul R., "Life cycle assessment of an integrated forest biorefinery: hot water extraction process case study, Biofuels, Bioproducts and Biorefining, Vol. 9, No. 6, 2015, pp. 677-695. doi: 10.1002/bbb.1570	UWM	Sugars and starch (non-polymerized)	Raw material	medium	IMPACT 2002+ method (version 2.15)						1	LCC and LCA	1	1
González-García, Sara., Hospido, Almudena., Agnemo, Roland., Svensson, Patrik., Selling, Eva., Moreira, Ma Teresa., and Feijoo, Gumerindo., "Environmental Life Cycle Assessment of a Swedish Dissolving Pulp Mill Integrated Biorefinery", <i>Journal of Industrial Ecology, Vol.15, No. 4, pp. 568-583.</i>	UWM	Sugars and starch (non-polymerized)	Raw material	good	CML 2 baseline 2000 V2.1 method	1					0	LCA	1	
Günther, Jazmin, Nieli Thevs, Hans-Jörg Gsovaius, Ina Sigmund, Torsten Brückner, Volker Beckmann, and Nurbay Abduhalik, "Carbon and phosphorus footprint of the cotton production in Xinjiang, China, in comparison to an alternative fibre (Apocynum) from Central Asia," <i>Journal of Cleaner Production Vol. 148, 2017, pp. 490-497</i>	ECOS	Fibres	Raw material	-	C FP and P FP (Brunner, P.H., Rechberger, H., 2004)						1	IO		1
Jorge Cristóbal, Cristina T. Matos, Jean-Philippe Aurbabou, Simone Manfredi, and Boyan Kavalov, "Environmental sustainability assessment of bioeconomy value chains", <i>Biomass and Bioenergy, Vol. 85, 2016, pp. 159-171 https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biombioe.2016.02.002</i>	UWM	Sugars and starch (non-polymerized)	Raw material	good	Custom set						1	LCA	1	
Krzyżaniak, Michał, Stolarski, Mariusz Jerzy., Szczukowski, Stefan, and Tworkowski, Józef, "Life Cycle Assessment of New Willow Cultivars Crown as Feedstock for Integrated Biorefineries", <i>Bioenergy Research, Vol. 9, No. 1, pp. 224-238. doi: 10.1007/s12155-015-9681-3</i>	UWM	Sugars and starch (non-polymerized)	Raw material	-	CML 2 baseline 2000	1					0	LCA	1	
Manógar, Mohsen Ali, Farzad, Somayeh., von Rensburg, Eugene., and Gørgens, Johann. F., "Multi-criteria analysis of a biorefinery for co-production of lactic acid and ethanol from sugarcane lignocellulose, Biofuels, Bioproducts and Biorefining, doi: 10.1002/bbb.1801 (in press)	UWM	Sugars and starch (non-polymerized)	Raw material	good	CML-IA baseline 3.2	1					0	LCC and LCA	1	1
Martijn L.M. Broeren, Stijn N.C. Dellaert, Benjamin Cok, Martin K. Patel, Ernst Worrell, Li Shen; "Life cycle assessment of sisal fibre e Exploring how local practices can influence environmental performance" <i>Journal of Cleaner Production 149 (2017) 819-827</i>	ECOS	Fibres	Raw material	-	ReCiPe Midpoint	1					0	LCA	1	
Martinez, S., Bessou, C., Hure, L., Guilbot, J., and Helias, A., "The impact of palm oil feedstock within the LCA of a bio-sourced cosmetic cream", <i>Journal of Cleaner Production, Vol. 145, 2017, pp. 348-360.</i>	UniBo	Oils (non-polymerized)	Raw material	-	ILCD 2011						1	LCA	1	
Murphy, Richard J. and Andrew Norton, "Life Cycle Assessments of Natural Fibre Insulation Materials" Published by National Non-Food Crops Centre, February 2008. http://nova-institut.de/news-images/20080306-05/lca_fibre.pdf	ECOS	Fibres	Raw material	-	CML	1					0	LCA	1	
Poopak, Sotodehnia, and Amir Roodan, "Environmental Benefit of Using Bagasse in Paper Production - A Case Study of LCA in Iran," <i>Global Warming - Impacts and Future Perspectives, 2012</i>	ECOS	Fibres	Raw material	-	CML 2000 Baseline	1					0	IO		1
Saravai, Anna Bernstad, Elen B.a.v. Pacheco, Gabriel M. Gomes, Leila Ly. Visconte, C.a. Bernardo, Carla L. Simões, and Antonio G. Soares, "Comparative lifecycle assessment of mango packaging made from a polyethylene/Natural fiber composite and from cardboard material," <i>Journal of Cleaner Production Vol. 139, 2016, pp. 1168-1180</i>	ECOS	Fibres	Raw material	-	ILCD 2011						1	LCA	1	
Secchi, Michela, Castellani, Valentina, Collina, Elea, Mirabella, Nadia, and Sala, Serenella, "Assessing eco-innovations in green chemistry: Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) of a cosmetic product with a bio-based ingredient", <i>Journal of Cleaner Production, Vol. 129, 2016, pp. 269-281.</i>	UniBo	Oils (non-polymerized)	Raw material	-	ILCD 2011, ReCiPe 2012, CML 2012, IMPACT 2002	1	1	1			0	LCA	1	
Souza, Alexandre., Watanabe, Marcos Djun Barbosa, Cavelett, Otavio, Ligaya, Cassia Maria Lie, and Bonomi, Antonio., "Social life cycle assessment of first and second-generation ethanol production technologies in Brazil", <i>The International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment, (in press), doi: 10.1007/s11367-016-1112-y</i>	UWM	Sugars and starch (non-polymerized)	Raw material	-	UNEP/SETAC SLCA guidelines						1	IO and SLCA	1	1
Spyros Foteinis, Victor Kouloumpis, and Theocharis Tsoutsos, "Life cycle analysis for bioethanol production from sugar beet crops in Greece", <i>Energy Policy, 39, 2011, 4834-4841.</i>	UWM	Sugars and starch (non-polymerized)	Raw material	medium	CML 2 baseline method, Eco-indicator 99	1					0	LCA	1	
Suwanmanee, Unchalee, Varabuntoonvit, Viganada, Chaiwitthinan, Phasawat, Tajan, Monchai, Mungchaoen Thumrongut, and Thanawadee Leelarkpai, "Life cycle assessment of single use thermoform boxes made from polystyrene (PS), polylactic acid, (PLA), and PLA/starch: cradle to consumer gate", <i>The International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment, Vol. 18, No. 2, 2013, pp. 401-</i>	UWM	Sugars and starch (non-polymerized)	Raw material	-	The Environmental Design of Industrial						1	LCA	1	
Vercalsteren An, Boonen Katrien, "Life Cycle Assessment study of starch products for the European starch industry association (Starch Europe): sector study", Report no. 2015/SMAT/R/0083, Flemish Institute for Technological Research NV"VITO", pp. 30	UWM	Sugars and starch (non-polymerized)	Raw material	good	ILCD 2011						1	LCA	1	
Yelin Deng, Yajun Tian, Assessing the Environmental Impact of Flax Fibre Reinforced Polymer Composite from a Consequential Life Cycle Assessment Perspective; Sustainability, 2015, Vol. 7, pp. 11462-11483	ECOS	Fibres	Raw material	-	ReCiPe Midpoint (H)	1					0	LCA	1	
Zhang, Yanan, Hu, Guijing and Brown, Robert C., "Life cycle assessment of a commodity chemical production from forest residue via fast pyrolysis", <i>International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment, Vol. 19, 2014, pp. 1371-1381.</i>	UniBo	Oils (non-polymerized)	Raw material	-	TRACI 2.0						1	LCA	1	
Zucaro, Amalia, Forte, Annachiara, Fagnano, Massimo, Bastianoni, Simone., Basosi, Riccardo, Fierro, Angelo., "Comparative attributional life cycle assessment of annual and perennial lignocellulosic	UWM	Sugars and starch (non-polymerized)	Raw material	good	ReCiPe H Ver 1.08 midpoint						1	LCA	1	

yes	yes				u							both								
yes		yes	yes	yes					yes									yes	yes	yes
								CED												
yes	yes				u															
yes	yes				u			CED			yes				EROI					
								CED												
	yes		yes	yes		yes														
														yes	yes	yes				
yes	yes				u						yes									
								CED							soil deterioration					
LOTOS-EUROS model	Accumulated exceedance model	Accumulated exceedance model	EUTREND model	EUTREND model		Swiss scarcity model	CML2002 model	Soil-organic matter model						yes						
	yes				u						yes									
yes	yes				u						yes									
									yes											
yes		yes	yes	yes				both	yes											
yes	yes				u						yes									
	yes				u						yes									
yes	yes	yes	yes	yes																
yes	yes	yes	yes	yes		yes	both	yes	yes	yes	yes									
	yes				u									yes	yes	yes				
yes	yes																			
yes	yes	yes	yes	yes		yes	yes	yes												
yes	yes		yes	yes		yes	both		yes	yes										
yes	yes				u			CED												
yes		yes	yes	yes		yes	yes													

0	0	0
0	0	0
0	0	0
13	20	15
13	20	15

